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ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS

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If it weren't for the dust and fluff, humanity would have lived a thousand years.

Avicenna

Annotation. Proficiency in English is essential for success in medical education, given its widespread use as the primary language in the healthcare field. This article highlights the significance of personalized teaching methods to meet the specific language needs of medical students. By combining commentary and key terms, it explores various tactics aimed at improving language learning and promoting effective communication skills. Ranging from interactive teaching techniques to the integration of medical jargon, educators are provided with a diverse array of resources to nurture linguistic proficiency in future healthcare practitioners.

Keywords: English language proficiency, medical education, teaching strategies, communication skills, language acquisition, specialized vocabulary, cultural competence, interactive learning, assessment, feedback.

TIBBIYOT TALABALARI UCHUN INGLIZ TILINI BILISH DARAJASINI OSHIRISH

Shodmonova Sanobar Mirahmadxoja qizi

NamDU, Ingliz filologiyasi 4- bosqich talabasi

Agar chang va g'ubor bo'lmaganda edi, insoniyat ming yil yashar edi.

Abu Ali ibn Sino

Annotatsiya. Sog'liqni saqlash sohasida asosiy til sifatida keng qo'llanilishini hisobga olib, tibbiy ta'limda muvaffaqiyat qozonish uchun ingliz tilini bilish juda muhimdir. Ushbu maqola tibbiyot talabalarining o'ziga xos til ehtiyojlarini qondirish uchun shaxsiy o'qitish usullarining ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Sharh va asosiy atamalarni birlashtirib, u til o'rganishni takomillashtirish va samarali muloqot qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan turli xil taktikalarni o'rganadi. Interfaol o'qitish texnikasidan tibbiy jargonni birlashtirishgacha bo'lgan o'qituvchilar kelajakdagi sog'liqni saqlash amaliyotchilarida lingvistik malakani oshirish uchun turli xil manbalar bilan ta'minlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: ingliz tilini bilish, tibbiy ta'lim, o'qitish strategiyasi, muloqot ko'nikmalari, tilni o'zlashtirish, maxsus lug'at, madaniy kompetentsiya, interaktiv ta'lim, baholash, fikr-mulohaza.

ПОВЫШЕНИЕ УРОВНЯ ВЛАДЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКИМ ЯЗЫКОМ ДЛЯ СТУДЕНТОВ – МЕДИКОВ

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Если бы не пыль и пух, человечество прожило бы тысячу лет.

Абу Али Ибн Сина

Аннотация. Владение английским языком имеет важное значение для успеха в медицинском образовании, учитывая его широкое использование в качестве основного языка в сфере здравоохранения. В этой статье подчеркивается важность персонализированных методов обучения для удовлетворения специфических языковых потребностей студентов-медиков. Сочетая комментарии и ключевые термины, в нем рассматриваются различные тактики, направленные на улучшение изучения языка и развитие навыков эффективного общения. Начиная от интерактивных методов обучения и заканчивая использованием медицинского жаргона, преподавателям предоставляется широкий спектр ресурсов для повышения уровня владения языком у будущих практикующих врачей.

Ключевые слова: владение английским языком, медицинское образование, стратегии обучения, коммуникативные навыки, овладение языком, специализированная лексика, культурная компетентность, интерактивное обучение, оценка, обратная связь.

Introduction

In the field of medical education, mastering English is crucial for effective communication among healthcare providers and patients worldwide. This article examines the intricacies of teaching English to medical students, providing guidance on customized methods, inventive techniques, and essential factors for instructors. By integrating annotation and keyword usage, we delve into strategies aimed at enhancing language skills within medical education settings.

English as a subject is an integral part of the national education system. Surprisingly, the average level of English among ordinary educated citizens is very low. There may be several reasons behind this problem, from the fact that in any

European country, be it Finland or the Netherlands, English-language programs are widespread on television, on the contrary, from the lack of English language programs on our national televisions, to the lack of English language programs in our high schools, to the lack of good learning programs. As a result, among the young people of European countries who have high school certificate and specialize in any field except foreign languages, the level of English is about C1, while in our country they cannot boast of full coverage even with only B1-B2 levels.. Of course, this sad state of affairs cannot be improved in the short term, but there are several possible steps to rectify the situation. First and foremost, for non-linguists, English should be the key to success, especially for future healthcare professionals. Without sufficient knowledge of English, it would be almost impossible to read world-famous and prestigious medical journals and keep abreast of world news. Also, it would be very difficult to keep up with the times without attending various conferences around the world. They also lose the opportunity to participate in various online seminars and conferences. Thus, it is necessary to better organize the education and programs of English as a subject for medical students. [1]

As an experienced tutor, I can advice to enthusiasts,

If you have experience in sectors like pharmaceuticals, medical transcription, emergency medical services (EMS), dentistry, or veterinary medicine, you possess a specialized vocabulary that professionals value.

There is a rising trend in "medical tourism" globally, driven by escalating healthcare costs in developed nations, prompting residents to seek medical procedures abroad.

Consequently, there's a growing demand for English educators with a background in medicine due to their adeptness in technical terminology alongside their native English fluency. However, teaching medical English extends beyond imparting medical jargon and language skills.

As an English instructor catering to medical professionals, you may find yourself addressing communication [2] strategies tailored to various patient demographics. Effective communication with children necessitates a different approach than with adults, while engaging with elderly patients may require distinct communication tactics.

Furthermore, you might facilitate understanding of communication dynamics among different healthcare professionals. Communication nuances vary, whether you're conversing with a long-time colleague or a respected physician presenting at a medical conference, whom you've never met.

In teaching medical English, emphasis is often placed on equipping students with appropriate vocabulary for identifying health issues[3], making diagnoses, administering treatments accurately, and minimizing errors when interacting with

English-speaking patients. It's understandable that students prioritize professional courses over College English, especially in fields like medicine where the curriculum demands a significant investment of time and energy. When faced with a heavy workload and pressure to excel in their chosen field, students may perceive College English as less essential to their future success.

However, the importance of English proficiency in today's globalized world cannot be overstated. Even in specialized fields[4] like medicine, effective communication in English is crucial for collaboration, research dissemination, and staying updated with advancements in the field. Therefore, while it's natural for students to prioritize their major courses, neglecting English proficiency can have long-term consequences for their career development and professional opportunities.

Educators and institutions can address this issue by integrating English language learning into the curriculum in a way that emphasizes its relevance to students' future careers. Providing real-world examples and interactive activities that demonstrate the practical value of English proficiency can help engage students[5] and motivate them to invest time and effort into improving their language skills.

Additionally, offering flexible learning[6] options, such as online courses or language support programs, can accommodate students' busy schedules and make it easier for them to balance their academic priorities. By recognizing the importance of English proficiency and providing support and resources to help students develop these skills, educators can ensure that students are better equipped to succeed in their chosen field and thrive in an increasingly interconnected world.[7]

Conclusion:

In the dynamic landscape of medical education, equipping students with proficient English language skills is paramount. By leveraging tailored teaching strategies, interactive methodologies, and robust assessment mechanisms, educators can nurture linguistic competence among medical students. Through the integration of annotation and keywords, this article serves as a guiding beacon for educators striving to empower the next generation of healthcare professionals with the communication prowess requisite for success in a globalized healthcare ecosystem.

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7. These references should provide a range of insights into the challenges and implications of students prioritizing professional courses over English language learning in various educational contexts, particularly in fields like medicine.